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IMITATIVE WORDS IN JAPANESE (COMPARATIVE GRAMMAR ANALYSIS OF UZBEK LANGUAGE)

Esmera Mardonova¹, Malikova Sitora²

¹UZSWLU final course, ²Supervisor Japanese language teacher at UzSWLU

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ABSTRACT

This article analyzes the use of imitation words in Japanese and Uzbek. The article was considered with various examples.

INTRODUCTION

In recent years, cooperation between Uzbekistan and Japan has expanded, and now cooperation is expanding not only in political but also in social, economic, scientific and other fields. In recent years, the number of Japanese language learners in Uzbekistan has been growing rapidly. Today, Japanese is studied in 130 countries around the world, and Uzbekistan ranks 35th in terms of the number of students. This is the highest rate in the world.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Tamori and Schourup (1999) sought to explore the linguistic world by comparing Japanese onomatopoeia with Indo-European imitation words (e.g., Japanese and English).

Yamaguchi (2001) studied the expressive meanings of onomatopoeia in manga. Rumak (2012) created the Japanese-Russian Annotated Dictionary of Onomatopoeic Vocabulary. Gomi (2000) has compiled a unique dictionary, The

Japanese Language and a Collection of Onomatopoeic Expressions.

There has been a lot of research on imitation words in Uzbek as well. U. Tursunov, A. Mukhtorov, Sh. Rahmatullayev, A. Nurmonov, A. Sobirov, Sh. Yusupova, A. Anorbekova, Sh. The research work of linguists such as Mirzayeva and R. Sayfullayeva is an example of this.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Japanese differs from other languages in its complexity. These are reflected in the written form and the specific grammatical forms and their semantic features. It should also be noted that the etymological evidence inherent in Japanese and the subtleties and differences of language that emerge in the process of learning that language are particularly complex for speakers of other languages. Examples include Japanese imitation words (onomatopoeic and mimetic words) that are widely used, from everyday speech to Japanese anime, and are very close in form and meaning.

Onomatopoeia is used to express ideas in a simple and figurative way through a combination of individual sounds. Vov-vov (dog barking), chiq-chiq (clock), ha-haha (laugh), jimir-jimir (water), yalt-yult (state of an object when light falls) This situation is the same in Uzbek and Japanese. But their classification is different.

Kristen Dexter divided thousands of onomatopoeia in Japanese into 5 types and scientifically substantiated the uniqueness of each species:

擬声語 Giseigo human voices and animal voices;

擬音語 Giongo inanimate objects and sounds associated with nature;

擬態語 Gitaigo imitation words that describe the state of a person or thing;

擬容語 Giyougo imitation words that describe the structure and appearance of a particular object;

擬情語 Gijougo imitation words that express emotions.

If we look at the name of this classification and its meanings through Japanese kanji, it will be easier to understand:

声 sei sound

音 on voice

態 tai condition, appearance

容 you shape, structure

情 jyou feeling

There are not many imitation words in Uzbek. There are 2 types, such as imitation of sound and state. But in terms of vocabulary, scientists are based on different theories. In particular, AN Kononov in his 13th work "Grammar of the Uzbek language" shows that imitation words are a form of exclamation words, and in his work "Grammar of the modern Turkish literary language" published in 1956 he divided them into separate word groups. Textbooks

(N.Mahmudov, A.Nurmonov "native language") state that word groups belong to the 3rd type, ie separate words.

Giseigo sounds of individuals and living beings (animals and birds)

にゃあ nyaa—miyov(cat), めえ mee—mee(sheep), こけこっこ kokekokko—

quququq(rooster). It is obvious that these metaphors are almost indistinguishable from the Uzbek metaphors. But, わんわん

van van—dog, ぴよぴよ pyo pyo—the chirping of birds, ちゅうちゅう chyuu

chyuu—mouse sound, けろけろ kerak kero—

The expressions of the frog's voice are not the same as in Uzbek.

猫はにゃあと鳴きながらこっちへ来た。

Nekova nyaa to nakinagara kochchie kita
The cat came this way while meowing.

犬がわんわんと人に向かって吠えていた。

Inuga van van to hitoni mukatte hoette ita
The dog barked at the man.

どこから羊がめえめえと鳴く声が聞こえる。

Dokokara hitsujiga meme to naku koega kikoeru

The sheep are barking somewhere.

擬音語(giongo)

擬音語 giongo—consists of all kinds of imitation words, from the roar of the wind to the ticking of the clock in connection with inanimate objects and nature..

誰かがドアをドンドンたたいています。

Darekaga doao dondon tataite imasu -
Someone is knocking on the door.

子供が嬉しそうにご飯をもぐもぐ食べている。

Kodomoga ureshisouni gohano moku moku tabete iru

The children are filling their mouths and chewing food.

風が強くてドアががたがたしている。

Kazega tsuyokute doaga gatagata tataitte iru

There is a knock on the door in the strong wind.

擬態語(gitaigo)

擬態語gitaigo appearance, the transition of things from one state to another, as well as the emotional expressions inherent in man are also considered to belong to this type.

つるつるtsuru tsuru—smooth, ざらざら zara zara—rough, ぐにゃぐにゃgunya gunya—soft or pliable, ぴかぴかpika pika—shiny etc. the quality of an object can be expressed vividly. Besides, ふらふらfura fura—trembling in the body, いらいらira ira—irritability, nervousness, ぼそぼそ boso boso—surprise, わくわくvaku vaku—metaphors for mood swings. There are no similarities compared to Uzbek. Because in Uzbek these expressions are considered to belong to the category of adjectives, verbs or forms and are not accepted as imitation words.

てくてく歩くteku teku aruku—reluctantly go;

へトへとに疲れるheto hetoni tsukareru—tired like a dog. In the Uzbek language, in

this case, it comes with a verb and a phrase, indicating its sign, and in the Japanese language, it has a similar meaning, but it is an imitation word.

星がきらきら光っている。Hoshiga kira kira hikatte iru

The stars are shining.

明日から日本へ行くのでわくわくしている。Asukara Nihonge ikunode vaku vaku shite iru

I am very happy to be going to Japan tomorrow.

今日は会社で怒られたのでいらいらしている。

Kyouva kaishyade okoraretanode ira ira shite iru

Today I am nervous because I was reprimanded at work. (Bugun ishda tanbeh berishgani uchun asabiylashyapman) The analysis of these statements shows that the imitation words in Japanese and Uzbek languages are similar in meaning, but differ in word group.

CONCLUSION

The analysis of these statements shows that the imitation words in Japanese and Uzbek languages are similar in meaning, but differ in word group.

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